

Machine Learning–Based Prediction of Organic Solar Cell Performance Using Molecular Descriptors

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Abstract: The performance of Organic Solar Cells (OSCs) is intrinsically linked to the molecular, electronic, and structural properties of donor and acceptor materials. This study employs various machine learning techniques, namely the Generalized Regression Neural Network (GRNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Tree Boost, to predict key performance metrics of OSCs, including power conversion efficiency (*PCE*), short-circuit current density (J_{SC}), open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}), and fill factor (*FF*). The models are trained and evaluated using an experimentally reported dataset compiled by Sahu et al. Correlation analysis demonstrates that material characteristics such as polarizability, bandgap, dipole moment, and charge transfer are statistically associated with OSC performance. The predictive performance of the GRNN model is compared with that of the SVM and Tree Boost models, showing consistently lower prediction errors within the considered dataset. In addition, sensitivity analysis is performed to assess the relative importance of the predictor variables and to examine the influence of kernel functions on GRNN performance. The results indicate that machine learning models, particularly GRNN, can serve as effective data-driven tools for predicting the performance of organic solar cells and for supporting computational screening studies.

Keywords: General Regression Neural Networks, Organic Solar Cells, Power Conversion Efficiency, Sensitivity Analysis, Support Vector Machine, Tree Boost.

1 INTRODUCTION

Traditional fossil energy sources are increasingly unable to meet the sustainable development needs of human society. This inadequacy stems from rising global energy consumption and the environmental impacts associated with fossil fuel extraction and combustion. In recent years, data-driven and machine-learning-based approaches have been increasingly explored to address complex challenges in energy materials research, including predicting photovoltaic device performance using experimentally reported datasets [1]. The harmful effects of fossil fuels, including greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution, further emphasize the urgent need for a transition toward cleaner and more sustainable energy alternatives [2]. Among renewable energy technologies, solar electricity has emerged as one of the most promising options. A solar cell, or photovoltaic device, converts light energy directly into electrical energy through the photovoltaic effect [3]-[5]. This process involves the absorption of photons by a semiconductor material, resulting in the generation of charge carriers that can be collected as electrical current [6].

Semiconductor materials, both organic and inorganic, play a crucial role in photon-to-electron conversion. Organic solar cells (OSCs) have attracted considerable attention due to their lightweight nature, mechanical flexibility, and potential for low-cost fabrication through solution processing and roll-to-roll manufacturing techniques [7][8]. Despite these advantages, OSCs have yet to achieve widespread commercial deployment, primarily due to their relatively lower *PCE* and limited operational stability compared to inorganic counterparts. Recent advances in material design and device architecture have enabled OSCs to achieve *PCEs* of approximately 13% [9]-[11]; however, this performance remains below that of mature inorganic photovoltaic technologies. Further improvements in OSC performance are hindered by the complexity of organic material synthesis and purification, as well as the extensive experimental effort required to evaluate new donor–acceptor combinations [12][13]. In addition, accurately predicting the *PCE* of OSCs from molecular structure remains difficult due to factors such as strong electron–phonon interactions, complex donor–acceptor interfaces, and the distinct charge-transport mechanisms in organic semiconductors [14][15].

To address the challenges associated with predicting organic solar cell performance, recent research has increasingly integrated computational methods with data-driven approaches. In the field of organic photovoltaics, machine learning techniques have been applied to establish relationships between quantum-chemical descriptors of organic materials and experimentally measured device performance metrics [16]-[20]. Beyond photovoltaics, machine learning has been widely used in drug discovery and molecular modeling [17,18], heterogeneous catalysis [21]-[22], reaction-mechanism studies [23]-[25], and materials discovery and screening [26]-[30]. These studies demonstrate the broad applicability of machine learning for analyzing complex structure–property relationships across scientific domains. Sahu et al. [1] showed that ensemble learning methods, such as gradient boosting, can effectively predict the *PCE* of organic solar cells using a set of molecular descriptors derived from quantum-chemical calculations. Their work highlighted the potential of ML-based models for predictive screening and analysis of OSC materials, motivating further investigation into alternative learning algorithms and expanded performance metrics.

Building upon this prior work, the present study evaluates the performance of three machine learning techniques, GRNN, SVM, and Tree Boost—for predicting key photovoltaic parameters of OSCs, including V_{OC} , J_{SC} , FF , and PCE . Using the same experimentally reported dataset compiled by Sahu et al. [1], this work focuses on comparative model evaluation, statistical performance assessment, and sensitivity analysis of molecular descriptors, without introducing new experimental data or material systems. The primary objectives of this study are to compare the predictive accuracy of GRNN, SVM, and Tree Boost models; to examine the relative influence of molecular descriptors on model predictions; and to assess the suitability of these machine learning techniques for data-driven analysis of organic solar cell performance.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Methodology

This study evaluates three machine learning–based methods, namely GRNN, SVM, and Tree Boost models, for predicting the photovoltaic performance parameters of organic solar cells, including V_{OC} , J_{SC} , FF , and PCE . The overall workflow of the study, including data preparation, model training, validation, and performance evaluation, is illustrated in Fig. 1. The objective of this methodological framework is to compare the predictive capabilities of different machine learning models using the same set of molecular descriptors and experimental performance data, rather than to introduce new descriptors or experimental measurements.

Fig. 1. A flowchart of the research steps.

2.2. Data Collection and Analysis

This study utilizes the database compiled by Sahu et al. which includes 280 small-molecule OSCs featuring 270 distinct donor materials [1]. The database contains 17 parameters: 4 output parameters (V_{OC} , J_{SC} , FF , and PCE) and 13 predictor (input) parameters, as shown in Table 1. The 13 parameters are defined as follows:

- i) polarizability of donor molecules
- ii) energetic difference of LUMO and LUMO+1 of acceptors Δ_L^A
- iii) number of unsaturated atoms in the main conjugation path of donor molecules N_{atom}^D
- iv) bandgap energy for the electron to transition to a singlet excited state with the largest oscillator strength E_g
- v) reorganization energy for holes in donor molecules λ_h
- vi) vertical ionization potential of donor molecules $IP(v)$
- vii) energy difference of HOMO of donor and LUMO of acceptor E_{HL}^{DA}
- viii) energy difference of HOMO and HOMO–1 of the donor molecules, $\Delta_H = E_{HOMO} - E_{HOMO-1}$
- ix) energy difference of LUMO and LUMO+1 of the donor molecules, $\Delta_L = E_{LUMO+1} - E_{LUMO}$
- x) hole–electron binding energy in donor molecules E_{bind} ,
- xi) energy difference of LUMO of donor and LUMO of acceptor E_{LL}^{DA}
- xii) change in dipole moment in going from the ground state to the first excited state for donor molecules Δge
- xiii) energy of the electronic transition to the lowest-lying triplet state E_{T1}

To provide a comprehensive overview of the dataset, various statistical measures were computed, including means, standard deviations, ranges, upper and lower 95% confidence values, medians, modes, and data limits. Table 1 displays the statistics for the parameter spectrum. Pre-analysis of the parameters identified gaps in the data distribution that should be considered during model training and validation. Despite the abundance of data, several gaps were noted. The V_{OC} range from approximately 0.36 to 1.11, while the FF values range from 0.32 to 0.76. Notably, the V_{OC} spectrum from 0.7 to 1.0 and the FF spectrum from 0.45 to 0.75 encompass 90% and 88% of all data, respectively. The J_{SC} values range from approximately 1.9 to 16.82, with 88% of the dataset covering the J_{SC} spectrum from 7.5 to 15. For PCE , values range from 0.5 to 9.84, with the spectrum from 3 to 8 covering 88% of all data.

Table 1. Parameters dataset descriptive statistics.

Parameter	Type	Number	Min.	Max.	Mean	Median	Mode	Std. Dev.
V_{OC}	Output	280	0.36	1.11	0.864	0.88	0.9	0.097
J_{SC}	Output	280	1.9	16.82	10.837	10.815	13.6	2.470
FF	Output	280	0.32	0.76	0.584	0.59	0.58	0.098
PCE	Output	280	0.5	9.84	5.426	5.245	4.4	1.687
<i>Polarizability</i>	Predictor	280	212.29	212.29	1113.549	1084.87	1267.35	398.196
Δ_L^A	Predictor	280	0.03	0.08	0.043	0.03	0.03	0.022
N_{atom}^D	Predictor	280	18	134	58.861	60	64	18.991
E_a	Predictor	280	389.92	638.27	487.224	484.345	454.6	43.191
λ_h	Predictor	280	0.08	0.79	0.388	0.38	0.36	0.1062
$IP(\nu)$	Predictor	280	5.79	7.51	6.380	6.36	6.18	0.245
E_{HL}^{DA}	Predictor	280	2.94	4.34	3.493	3.485	3.59	0.217
Δ_H	Predictor	280	0.03	2.18	0.465	0.4	0.39	0.325
Δ_L	Predictor	280	0	2.07	0.363	0.185	0.05	0.486
E_{bind}	Predictor	280	1.63	3.16	2.140	2.1	2.07	0.212
E_{LL}^{DA}	Predictor	280	-0.56	1.24	0.489	0.51	0.53	0.225
Δ_{ge}	Predictor	280	0	31.16	1.578	0.615	0	3.370
E_{T1}	Predictor	280	0.76	2.39	1.610	1.7	1.16	0.335

The mean polarizability is 1113.549, with 94% of the tests falling within the range 250 to 1750. For the parameter Δ_L^A , 73% of the tests fall within the range of 0.03 to 0.035, while 27% are within 0.08 to 0.085. The variable N_{atom}^D follows a normal distribution, ranging from 18 to 34, with an average value of 58.86. Notably, 94% of tests for N_{atom}^D fall within the range of 20 to 90. For other parameters, E_g , λ_h , $IP(\nu)$, and E_{HL}^{DA} cover 88%, 93%, 90%, and 88% of tests, respectively, within the ranges of 425 to 550, 0.2 to 0.6, 6.00 to 6.75, and 3.2 to 3.8. The values for Δ_H and Δ_L approximate 0.03 to 2.18 and 0 to 2.07, respectively, with the spectra from 0 to 0.75 covering 88% and 86% of all data for Δ_H and Δ_L , respectively. The parameters E_{bind} , E_{LL}^{DA} , Δ_{ge} , and E_{T1} cover 93%, 97%, 93%, and 95% of the tests, with ranges of 1.75 to 2.5, 0.00 to 1.00, 0.00 to 2.00, and 1.00 to 2.00, respectively.

To enhance understanding of the relationships among these parameters and their mutual effects, correlation analysis was conducted. Correlation values range between -1 and +1, where -1 indicates a strong negative correlation, +1 indicates a strong positive correlation, and 0 implies no linear correlation. Table 2 displays the correlation matrix for the feature variables. The correlation matrix reveals several noteworthy relationships between the variables. Polarizability shows strong negative correlations with Δ_L (-0.531), N_{atom}^D (0.9087), E_{bind} (-0.707), and PCE (0.507). This indicates that higher polarizability is statistically associated with lower Δ_L , smaller molecular size, weaker binding energy, and higher reported photovoltaic performance within the dataset. Additionally, the ionization potential ($IP(\nu)$) and the electron affinity of the donor material (E_{HL}^{DA}) are closely linked, which is critical for charge transport and separation in organic solar cells. The bandgap energy (E_g) exhibits a strong negative correlation with $IP(\nu)$ (-0.636) and E_{HL}^{DA} (-0.647), indicating that a lower bandgap is associated with a higher dipole moment and better charge transfer.

Table 2. Correlation matrix of the feature variables.

	Polarizability	Δ_L^A	Δ_L	N_{atom}^D	E_g	λ_h	$IP(\nu)$	E_{HL}^{DA}	Δ_H	E_{bind}	E_{LL}^{DA}	Δ_{ge}	E_{T1}	$V_{oc}(V)$	J_{SC}	FF	PCE
Polarizability	1.000	-0.066	-0.531	0.908	0.361	-0.167	-0.530	-0.350	-0.594	-0.707	-0.239	-0.240	-0.008	-0.020	0.440	0.379	0.507
Δ_L^A	-0.066	1.000	0.046	-0.047	0.146	-0.062	0.024	-0.129	0.099	0.128	0.128	-0.073	-0.078	-0.175	-0.269	-0.184	-0.364
Δ_L	-0.531	0.046	1.000	-0.531	-0.003	-0.042	0.130	-0.039	0.431	0.558	0.200	0.201	-0.335	-0.193	-0.232	-0.430	-0.410
N_{atom}^D	0.908	-0.047	-0.531	1.000	0.387	-0.144	-0.483	-0.335	-0.609	-0.586	-0.201	-0.323	-0.105	-0.098	0.443	0.466	0.525
E_g	0.361	0.146	-0.003	0.387	1.000	-0.165	-0.636	-0.647	-0.182	-0.279	-0.290	-0.273	-0.683	-0.500	0.325	0.020	0.074
λ_h	-0.167	-0.062	-0.042	-0.144	-0.165	1.000	0.131	0.146	-0.033	0.087	0.114	-0.044	0.111	0.000	-0.077	-0.024	-0.113
$IP(\nu)$	-0.530	0.024	0.130	-0.483	-0.636	0.131	1.000	0.958	0.288	0.425	-0.235	0.382	0.344	0.372	-0.278	-0.108	-0.134
E_{HL}^{DA}	-0.350	-0.129	-0.039	-0.335	-0.647	0.146	0.958	1.000	0.129	0.224	-0.350	0.370	0.431	0.476	-0.155	-0.017	0.030
Δ_H	-0.594	0.099	0.431	-0.609	-0.182	-0.033	0.288	0.129	1.000	0.518	0.169	0.185	-0.025	-0.062	-0.378	-0.261	-0.383
E_{bind}	-0.707	0.128	0.558	-0.586	-0.279	0.087	0.425	0.224	0.518	1.000	0.455	-0.025	-0.167	-0.077	-0.383	-0.402	-0.504
E_{LL}^{DA}	-0.239	0.128	0.200	-0.201	-0.290	0.114	-0.235	-0.350	0.169	0.455	1.000	-0.291	0.177	-0.059	-0.328	-0.192	-0.344
Δ_{ge}	-0.240	-0.073	0.201	-0.323	-0.273	-0.044	0.382	0.370	0.185	-0.025	-0.291	1.000	0.239	0.162	-0.072	-0.072	-0.029
E_{T1}	-0.008	-0.078	-0.335	-0.105	-0.683	0.111	0.344	0.431	-0.025	-0.167	0.177	0.239	1.000	0.506	-0.116	0.153	0.164
$V_{oc}(V)$	-0.020	-0.175	-0.193	-0.098	-0.500	0.000	0.372	0.476	-0.062	-0.077	-0.059	0.162	0.506	1.000	-0.161	-0.105	0.163
J_{SC}	0.440	-0.269	-0.232	0.443	0.325	-0.077	-0.278	-0.155	-0.378	-0.383	-0.328	-0.072	-0.116	-0.161	1.000	0.306	0.768
FF	0.379	-0.184	-0.430	0.466	0.020	-0.024	-0.108	-0.017	-0.261	-0.402	-0.192	-0.072	0.153	-0.105	0.306	1.000	0.722
PCE (%)	0.507	-0.364	-0.410	0.525	0.074	-0.113	-0.134	0.030	-0.383	-0.504	-0.344	-0.029	0.164	0.163	0.768	0.722	1.000

Short-circuit current density (J_{SC}) demonstrates moderate to strong positive correlations with N_{atom}^D (0.443), FF (0.306), and PCE (0.768). This suggests that larger molecules, higher fill factors, and better overall power conversion efficiency are associated with higher short-circuit current density. Furthermore, V_{oc} has a moderate positive correlation with $IP(\nu)$ (0.372) and E_{HL}^{DA} (0.476), implying that a higher dipole moment and better charge transfer contribute to an increased open-circuit voltage. The fill factor (FF) is also strongly correlated with PCE , indicating that optimizing the FF is crucial for achieving high-efficiency devices. The results of the analysis suggest that certain material properties, such as polarizability, bandgap, dipole moment, and charge transfer, exhibit strong statistical associations with the photovoltaic performance of organic materials.

The data suggest that variations in these properties are correlated with changes in photovoltaic performance, characterized by J_{SC} , V_{OC} , FF , and PCE . Further investigation into the specific relationships and underlying mechanisms could provide valuable insights into the design and development of efficient organic photovoltaic materials. Variations in material properties and device characteristics are associated with changes in J_{SC} and PCE . Additionally, minimizing resistive losses and reducing recombination can enhance the FF , which in turn can substantially boost overall PCE .

2.3. ML Techniques

The goal of machine learning techniques is to develop accurate predictive approximations that are computationally efficient and cost-effective while maintaining reasonable training time.

2.3.1. Generalized Regression Neural Network

GRNNs [31], [32], [33], [34], [35] are feedforward networks that utilize a learning mechanism based on nonlinear regression. During GRNN training, each training pattern is retained, allowing the network to operate as a single-pass learning model without relying on iterative backpropagation. A typical GRNN consists of four successive layers: initiated with the input layer, followed by the pattern (radial basis) layer, then by the summation layer, and culmination with the output layer, as demonstrated in the schematic diagram [34] in Fig. 2. Notably, the pattern layer has the same number of neurons as the training data points. The pattern layer's output is then fed into the summation layer, which contains neurons in both the numerator and denominator. This means that the neurons in the summation layer aggregate the outputs of the pattern layer. The number of elements of the resulting output vector (y) is equal to the number of numerator neurons.

Fig. 2. A GRNN's schematic diagram [34]

The output from the summation layer can then be transferred to the output layer. The value of the prediction (y) for an unknown input vector (x) is expressed as Eq. (1).

$$y = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i e^{-D(x,x_i)}}{\sum_{i=1}^n e^{-D(x,x_i)}} \quad (1)$$

where x represents the input vector, x_i represents the i^{th} case vector, W_i represents the weight connecting the i^{th} neuron in the pattern layer to the summation layer, D represents the Gaussian function, and n represents the number of training patterns of an input vector. The training procedure may be executed through multiple iterations employing various smoothing factors until the network is refined to achieve the minimum mean square error or a pre-defined threshold. The learning process can be interpreted as the construction of a multidimensional response surface that provides a statistically smooth approximation of the dataset [31], [33], [34], [36].

2.3.2. Support Vector Machine Methods

Originally developed for pattern-recognition tasks, the support vector machine approach has been extended to estimate nonlinear regression models by incorporating the ϵ -insensitive loss function [37]. The fundamental principle of SVM regression is to transform the original input data x into a higher-dimensional feature space through a nonlinear mapping and then solve a linear regression problem in that space. The SVM regression function is

$$f(x) = [w \cdot \phi(x)] + b \tag{2}$$

where $\phi(x)$ represent the nonlinear mapping function, w denotes the weight vector, and b specify the bias term. An estimation of the values for w and b is obtained by minimizing the regularized risk function. Hence, the regression function is

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^l (\delta_i - \delta_i^*) K(x_i, x) + b \tag{3}$$

The kernel function $K(x_i, x)$ is defined over the Lagrangian multipliers, and the support vectors are the data points corresponding to $\delta_i - \delta_i^* \neq 0$. In this study, the radial basis kernel function (RBF) $K(x_i, x) = e^{(-\|x_i - x\|^2 / 2\delta^2)}$ was employed, where δ^2 represents the kernel parameter controlling the width of the RBF kernel.

2.3.3. Tree Boost Method

The tree boost approach [38] is a member of the boosted regression tree family of theoretical modeling techniques. Through the integration of a boosting technique, Tree boost enhances the decision tree algorithm. Instead of constructing a single optimal model, the fundamental concept here is to merge a collection of weak models to produce a robust consensus single model. The tree boost algorithm generates new decision trees in a sequential manner by decreasing the residuals of original trees. The procedure of constructing this sequential model is a form of functional gradient descent. This approach can incorporate both qualitative and quantitative factors in the regression analysis. Moreover, correlated predictive variables and missing data can be handled using it. Furthermore, the method is generally considered to be robust to outliers and to the presence of less relevant predictor variables. The Tree boost model typically defines three primary parameters: the learning rate (also known as the shrinkage parameter), the complexity of the tree, and the number of regression trees (tree size). To evaluate the generalization of the Tree Boost model and mitigate overfitting, cross-validation techniques are employed. The machine learning models investigated in this study were assessed using the statistical metrics summarized in Table 3. The statistical measures given in Table 3 was employed to determine the ML-based models that were investigated in this study.

Table 3. Descriptions of the statistical measures.

Features	Definition	Description
<i>MSE</i>	Mean Squared Error	$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (P_i - O_i)^2$
<i>MAE</i>	Mean Absolute Error	$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N P_i - O_i $
<i>RMSE</i>	Root Mean Square Error	$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (P_i - O_i)^2}$
<i>SI</i>	Scatter Index	$SI = \frac{RMSE}{\bar{O}}$
<i>R</i>	Correlation Coefficient	$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (P_i - \bar{P})(O_i - \bar{O})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (P_i - \bar{P})^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - \bar{O})^2}}$
O_i , P_i , N , \bar{O} , and \bar{P} denote the observed value, predicted value, total number of data points, observations mean value, and predictions mean value.		

2.4. Resampling

The dataset was divided into two stages: training dataset and testing/validation dataset. Seventy percent of the dataset is selected at random for training, while thirty percent is reserved for validation. In the training stage, the subset is processed to determine the most suitable model parameters. After training, the models underwent testing to assess how effectively they could apply the knowledge they had acquired to new, unseen instances. Resampling methods involve taking samples from a dataset and fitting a model for every carried sample and obtaining insights into the adjusted model. Generally used resampling techniques include cross-validation techniques, such as leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) and k-fold cross-validation, as well as bootstrapping. Nevertheless, as noted in the research by [39], bootstrapping is not effective for identifying outliers. For this study, LOOCV was utilized. LOOCV requires dividing a set of instances into two separate parts. Rather than forming two subsets, one instance (x_1, y_1) is utilized to test and validate the ML models, while the remaining observations $\{(x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$ are used to train the ML models. The statistical learning technique is applied to the $n-1$ training instances, and a prediction (\hat{y}_1) is made for the excluded instances using its x_1 value.

Since (x_1, y_1) is not included in the fitting process, it provides an estimate of the test error based on the mean square error $MSE1 = (y_1 - \hat{y}_1)^2$, which is nearly unbiased. Despite its impartial nature, $MSE1$ is not a reliable estimate of test error because it depends on a single observation (x_1, y_1) and is highly variable. This method can be repeated multiple times to generate a series of test errors, $MSE1, \dots, MSE_n$. As a result, the LOOCV estimation for the overall test error MSE is calculated by averaging the n test error estimations, [40] as follows:

$$CV_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n MSE_i \tag{4}$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data preprocessing was necessary before supplying the training patterns to the network. Below is a linear normalizing function ranging from 0 to 1.

$$S = \frac{(X - X_{min})}{(X_{max} - X_{min})} \tag{5}$$

where S represents the normalized value of variable X , the value X_{min} represents the minimum variable value, and the value of X_{max} represents the maximum variable value.

3.1. Prediction V_{oc}

The results for each model were achieved using the training parameters listed in Table 4. Fig. 3 illustrates the correlations between the actual and predicted V_{oc} values from the machine learning models. Overall, the predicted values from the three models closely match the actual V_{oc} values, indicating strong performance in predicting V_{oc} . The GRNN model provides the closest predictions to the actual V_{oc} values, with its predicted values aligning very closely with the actual measurements. The Tree Boost and SVM models also demonstrate reasonably accurate predictions, exhibiting slight deviations from the actual values while maintaining a high level of agreement.

Table 5 presents a comparative analysis of the three machine learning models based on various performance metrics, including error analysis by computing the mean squared error (MSE), the mean absolute error (MAE), and the root mean squared error ($RMSE$), in addition to the scatter index (SI) and the correlation coefficient (R). The GRNN model exhibits the lowest MSE (0.002), MAE (0.038), $RMSE$ (0.048), and SI (0.055), indicating the highest accuracy among the three models. The correlation coefficients (R) indicate that the GRNN model has the strongest correlation with the actual V_{oc} values (0.871), followed by the Tree Boost model (0.825) and the SVM model (0.767).

Based on the analysis, the GRNN model is the most accurate and reliable among the three machine learning models for predicting V_{oc} values. The Tree Boost model also demonstrates strong performance, achieving the second-best results across the various metrics. While the SVM model remains reasonably accurate, it performs the weakest of the three models based on the provided metrics.

Fig. 3. Scatter plots of the actual and predicted V_{oc} values based on different ML-models.

Table 4. Model parameters of machine learning models.

Model	Parameters
GRNN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type analysis: regression - Validation method: Leave-one-out - Training method: conjugate gradient algorithm. - Kernel function: Gaussian; sigma (For <i>FF</i> prediction: σ polarizability=0.6776963, $\Delta_L^A = 0.883$, $\sigma N_{atom}^D=0.384$, $\sigma Eg=1.135$, $\sigma \lambda h=1.639$, $\sigma IP(v)=0.977$, $\sigma E_{HL}^{DA}=1.178$, $\sigma \Delta H=0.363$, $\sigma \Delta_L=0.304$, $\sigma E_{bind}=0.368$, $\sigma E_{LL}^{DA}=0.977$, $\sigma \Delta ge=1.642$, and $\sigma E_{T1}=0.999$); (For <i>J_{SC}</i> prediction: σ polarizability=0.968, $\Delta_L^A = 0.0001$, $\sigma N_{atom}^D=1.342$, $\sigma Eg=1.566$, $\sigma \lambda h=1.203$, $\sigma IP(v)=1.365$, $\sigma E_{HL}^{DA}=1.654$, $\sigma \Delta H=1.187$, $\sigma \Delta_L=0.3571501$, $\sigma E_{bind}=0.308$, $\sigma E_{LL}^{DA}=0.640$, $\sigma \Delta ge=1.692$, and $\sigma E_{T1}=0.856$); (For <i>V_{OC}</i> prediction: σ polarizability = 1.131, $\sigma \Delta_L^A = 0.695$, $\sigma N_{atom}^D=0.905$, $\sigma Eg=0.810$, $\sigma \lambda h=2.480$, $\sigma IP(v)=1.370$, $\sigma E_{HL}^{DA}=0.547$, $\sigma \Delta H=1.847$, $\sigma \Delta_L=0.988$, $\sigma E_{bind}=0.887$, $\sigma E_{LL}^{DA}=1.918$, $\sigma \Delta ge=2.003$, and $\sigma E_{T1}=0.264$); and (For <i>PCE</i> prediction: σ polarizability = 1.428, $\sigma \Delta_L^A = 0.001$, $\sigma N_{atom}^D=0.819$, $\sigma Eg=1.267$, $\sigma \lambda h=0.614$, $\sigma IP(v)=1.070$, $\sigma E_{HL}^{DA}=0.976$, $\sigma \Delta H=0.994$, $\sigma \Delta_L=0.548$, $\sigma E_{bind}=0.5748208$, $\sigma E_{LL}^{DA}=0.3323371$, $\sigma \Delta ge=0.813$, and $\sigma E_{T1}=0.953$); - Number of neurons prediction of <i>V_{OC}</i> = 117, of <i>J_{SC}</i> = 123, of <i>FF</i> = 140, and of <i>PCE</i> = 135.
SVM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type of SVM model: Regression (Epsilon-SVR) - Kernel function: Radial Basis Function (RBF) - Validation method: cross-validation, and number of cross-validation folds = 10 - Free parameters of kernel function: (for <i>V_{OC}</i> prediction: $\epsilon = 0.5$, Epsilon = 0.001, $C = 0.309$, $\gamma = 7.305$, and $P = 0.001$); (for <i>J_{SC}</i> prediction: $\epsilon = 0.5$, Epsilon = 0.001, $C = 8.245$, $\gamma = 1.072$, and $P = 1.092$); (for <i>FF</i> prediction: $\epsilon = 0.5$, Epsilon = 0.001, $C = 0.17562631$, $\gamma = 22.1668039$, and $P = 0.04319476$); (for <i>PCE</i> prediction: $\epsilon = 0.5$, Epsilon = 0.001, $C = 39.320$, $\gamma = 0.422$, and $P = 0.870$).
Tree Bost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type analysis: regression - Type of model: Tree Boost series of trees - Validation method: Random sampling (20%) - Maximum trees in Tree Boost series = 400 - Maximum splitting levels = 5 - Minimum size node to split = 10 - Max. categories for continuous predictors: 1000 - Tree pruning criterion: Minimum absolute error. - Average number of group splits in each tree: for <i>V_{OC}</i> prediction = 8.7; <i>J_{SC}</i> prediction = 8.2; for <i>FF</i> prediction = 8.9; and <i>PCE</i> prediction = 9.4. - Learning rate = 0.05

Additionally, all models significantly overestimated the *V_{OC}* values, as indicated by mean squared error. A comparison of the GRNN model outcomes with those of the other models suggested that the scatter index (*SI*) of the GRNN was 14.79% and 30.56% lower than that of the Tree Boost and SVM models, respectively (Fig. 4). Given the high accuracy and reliable performance of the GRNN model, it could be considered the preferred choice for *V_{OC}* prediction in this context. The Taylor diagram visually represents the performance of various ANN and SVM models using *R²*, *RMSE*, and standard deviation. It maps predicted values against actual values to illustrate their level of agreement. The diagram features horizontal and vertical axes, along with circular and radial lines to depict standard deviation, *RMSE*, and *R²* score, respectively. A model's accuracy is indicated by its proximity to the actual values.

Table 5. Error statistics for the ML models.

Prediction	Models	Error statistics				
		MSE	MAE	RMSE	SI	R
Voc	TB	0.003	0.043	0.055	0.064	0.825
	GRNN	0.002	0.038	0.048	0.055	0.871
	SVM	0.004	0.051	0.062	0.072	0.767
Jsc	TB	2.365	1.252	1.538	0.142	0.787
	GRNN	2.005	1.128	1.416	0.131	0.819
	SVM	3.297	1.485	1.816	0.168	0.678
FF	TB	0.004	0.055	0.065	0.112	0.743
	GRNN	0.003	0.042	0.051	0.088	0.850
	SVM	0.005	0.058	0.070	0.119	0.712
PCE	TB	1.039	0.828	1.019	0.188	0.800
	GRNN	0.780	0.705	0.883	0.163	0.852
	SVM	1.180	0.895	1.086	0.200	0.766

In this case, the GRNN model outperforms the other models (Tree Boost and SVM) by achieving a higher R^2 score, a greater standard deviation, and a lower $RMSE$. As shown in Fig. 5, the GRNN model is notably more reliable and closer to the actual values.

Fig. 4. Scatter index and correlation coefficient comparison for the ML-models.

3.2. Prediction J_{sc}

Fig. 6 illustrates the relationship between the actual and predicted values of J_{sc} based on the machine learning models. The GRNN model generally provides the closest predictions to the actual values, followed by the Tree Boost and SVM models. However, there are instances where predictions deviate significantly from the actual values, particularly for the SVM and Tree Boost models. Based on the analysis, the GRNN model appears to be the effective in predicting J_{sc} values among the three models. The lower error metrics (MSE , MAE , $RMSE$, SI) and higher R value indicate that the GRNN model is better equipped to capture the underlying patterns in the data and provide more accurate predictions. When comparing the results, the GRNN model demonstrated percentage improvements in SI of 8.60% and 28.24% over the Tree Boost and SVM models, respectively. These results highlight that the predictions of the GRNN model align more closely with the actual values than those of the other models. Overall, the prediction results from the GRNN model are more precise than those from the Tree Boost and SVM models. As shown in the Taylor diagram visualization (Fig. 5), the GRNN model is closer to the actual values than both the Tree Boost and SVM models, making it marginally more reliable.

Fig. 5. Taylor diagram visualization of ML models performance.

Fig. 6. Scatter plots of the actual and predicted J_{sc} values based on different models.

3.3. Prediction *FF*

Using a similar methodology, an evaluation was conducted to compare the effectiveness of different machine learning models in predicting the fill factor (*FF*). Fig. 7 illustrates the correlations between the actual and predicted values of *FF* based on the machine learning models. Overall, the models capture the general trend of the actual *FF* values, although some discrepancies are evident, particularly for lower actual values.

Fig. 7. Scatter plots of the actual and predicted *FF* values based on different models.

The GRNN model emerges as the most accurate among the three, with predictions that are closest to the actual values. Based on the performance metrics, the GRNN model outperforms the others, showcasing the lowest mean squared error (*MSE*) of 0.003, mean absolute error (*MAE*) of 0.042, root mean squared error (*RMSE*) of 0.051, and scatter index (*SI*) of 0.088, indicating superior overall accuracy. Additionally, the GRNN model has the highest correlation coefficient (*R*) value of 0.850, suggesting a strong correlation between the actual and predicted values. In terms of *SI*, the GRNN model exhibits percentage improvements of 27.29% and 35.55% over the Tree Boost and SVM models, respectively. The Taylor diagram visualization further confirms that the GRNN model is marginally more reliable and aligns more closely with the actual values compared to the Tree Boost and SVM models. Thus, the GRNN model appears to be the most suitable choice among the three for this dataset and prediction task.

3.4. Prediction *PCE*

Fig. 9 illustrates the correlations between the actual and predicted values of power conversion efficiency (*PCE*) as determined by the machine learning models. The comparison of actual and predicted values shows that the GRNN model generally provides the closest predictions, followed by the Tree Boost model and then the SVM model. The GRNN model boasts the lowest mean squared error (*MSE*) of 0.780, mean absolute error (*MAE*) of 0.705, and root mean squared error (*RMSE*) of 0.883, indicating the best overall accuracy in predicting *PCE* values. Additionally, it has the lowest scatter index (*SI*) of 0.163, reflecting the least amount of relative error in its predictions. The GRNN model also achieves the highest correlation coefficient (*R*-value) of 0.852, suggesting a strong correlation between the actual and predicted values. Based on the data provided, the GRNN model appears to be the best-performing model for predicting *PCE* values. It consistently outperforms the SVM and Tree Boost models across all evaluated performance metrics. Specifically, the *SI* of the GRNN model improved by 15.41% and 23.01% over the SVM and Tree Boost models, respectively. As shown in the Taylor diagram, the GRNN model is more accurate than the other models in terms of *R*² score, standard deviation, and *RMSE*. The GRNN model stands out as an effective model for predicting *PCE* values, demonstrating superior performance compared to the SVM and Tree Boost models across all metrics evaluated.

3.5. Comparison of GRNN with Previous Studies

A comparative analysis was conducted to assess the performance of the GRNN model in relation to the gradient boosting model proposed by [1] for predicting power conversion efficiency (*PCE*). The results indicate that the GRNN model demonstrates significantly superior performance compared to the gradient boosting model. As shown in Fig. 9, the GRNN model achieves a reduced root mean square error (*RMSE*) of 0.883, while the Sahu et al. model has an *RMSE* of 1.07. Additionally, the GRNN model exhibits a higher correlation coefficient (*R* value) of 0.852, in contrast to the model's *R* value of 0.79.

Fig. 8. Scatter plots of the actual and predicted PCE values based on different models.

Fig. 9. Comparison between GRNN model and the gradient boosting model by [1] model.

4 SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

4.1. Sensitivity Analysis of the Significance of Predictor Variables

To assess the importance of predictor variables in the GRNN model, cross-validation was employed. The sensitivity analysis was utilized in the computation, whereby each variable values were randomly assigned and the effect on the model's quality was evaluated. For V_{OC} , the analysis showed that E_{T1} (24.15%) was the most significant predictor, followed by E_{HL}^{DA} (18.85%), Δ_L (15.58%), Δ_{ge} (13.45%), N_{atom}^D (7.09%), E_{bind} (6.36%), Δ_L^A (4.17%), polarizability (4.11%), E_g (2.36%), Δ_H (1.85%), λ_h (1.30%), $IP(v)$ (0.41%) and E_{LL}^{DA} (0.32%). Fig. 10 shows the significance of the predictor variables. For J_{SC} , the analysis revealed that Δ_L^A (32.15%) was the most significant predictor, followed by E_{bind} (24.83%), Δ_L (15.30%), E_{LL}^{DA} (12.70%), Δ_{ge} (5.97%), polarizability (3.07%), Δ_H (2.088%), λ_h (1.22%), $IP(v)$ (0.51%), E_g (0.42%), E_{T1} (0.38%), N_{atom}^D (0.30%), and E_{HL}^{DA} (0.00%). For FF , the analysis revealed that N_{atom}^D (26.14%) was the most significant predictor, followed by Δ_L (20.45%), E_{bind} (19.83%), Δ_H (12.96%), Δ_{ge} (9.89%), $IP(v)$ (3.86%), polarizability (2.69%), E_{LL}^{DA} (1.97%), E_g (0.96%), E_{HL}^{DA} (0.94%), E_{T1} (0.22%), λ_h (0.07%), and Δ_L^A (0.00%). For PCE , the analysis revealed that Δ_L^A (22.12%) was the most significant predictor, followed by Δ_L (15.56%), E_{bind} (11.26%), Δ_{ge} (11.26%), λ_h (11.19%), N_{atom}^D (10.04%), E_{HL}^{DA} (5.32%), $IP(v)$ (4.40%), Δ_H (3.96%), E_{LL}^{DA} (1.78%), polarizability (1.4%), E_g (1.14%), and E_{T1} (0.58%).

These insights can focus on the most influential variables in data collection, feature engineering, and model optimization, potentially improving model performance. Overall, the analysis suggests that the most important variables in predicting the performance metrics of organic solar cells are Δ_L , E_{bind} , Δ_L^A and Δ_{ge} . These variables consistently have high importance across multiple performance metrics. Other variables like N_{atom}^D , E_{T1} , E_{HL}^{DA} and λ_h also play a significant role in predicting certain performance metrics.

Fig. 10. Significance of the predictor variables.

The analysis also highlights variables that may have less impact on the model's performance, which could potentially be removed or given less weight in the input vector, simplifying the model and improving its generalization. Overall, the deep analysis of the predictor variable importance provides valuable insights that can be used to enhance the development and optimization of the GRNN model for predicting the performance metrics of Organic Solar Cells.

4.2. Sensitivity analysis of the predictors

The objective here is to quantify the responsiveness of the produced GRNN model to the input factors (predictors), which were introduced earlier in Table 1. This was implemented by eliminating a single input element from the input factors for each computation, and then computing the resulting errors. Tables 6 to 9 provide a concise summary of the outcomes obtained from several simulations employing the GRNN model.

In each simulation, only one input element inside the input vector was altered. Percentage error is the measure of the final magnitude of the input vector in a model. Upon comparing the *SI* values, it becomes apparent that the GRNN model is more sensitive to certain parameters than to others. First, the model relies on E_{bind} for V_{OC} prediction, as evidenced by the higher *SI* value (25.455%) when the E_{bind} parameters are removed. Furthermore, E_{HL}^{DA} , λ_h , and Δ_L^A had a significant impact, with a respective change in *SI* of 12.727%, 12.727%, and 10.909%, respectively. Therefore, the crucial factors are Δ_{ge} , N_{atom}^D , and Δ_L , which collectively raise the *SI* from 1.818 to 3.636% when they are excluded. Values of $IP(v)$, E_{TI} , E_g , *polarizability*, and Δ_H are not statistically significant.

For J_{SC} prediction, λ_h , Δ_L , and Δ_H are the parameters that, when omitted, reduce the *SI* to 12.214%, 10.992%, and 9.160%, respectively. Δ_L^A and N_{atom}^D are the parameters that, when omitted, reduce the *SI* to 2.290% and 1.527%, respectively. Particularly intriguing is the similar impact of *polarizability*, E_{TI} , E_{HL}^{DA} , E_g , and $IP(v)$ (0.763%). Whereas parameters Δ_{ge} , E_{LL}^{DA} , and E_{bind} appear to have no significant. For FF prediction, first, the FF model presented dependence on Δ_L as established by the increased value of the *SI* (21.591%) when the Δ_L parameter is eliminated. Next, parameters E_g and Δ_L^A play a crucial role (with an *SI* increase of 17.046%, and 15.909%, respectively). The parameter (E_{bind}) causes the *SI* to increase from 3.409%. Particularly intriguing is the similar impact of λ_h and Δ_H of (2.273%). Also, the parameters $IP(v)$, N_{atom}^D , E_{TI} , and E_{HL}^{DA} have the same impact (1.136%). The parameters E_{LL}^{DA} , *polarizability*, and Δ_{ge} have no significant.

Table 6. Sensitivity analysis for GRNN model (V_{OC} prediction).

Predictor element elimination	No. of predictors elements	SI	% of variation of SI	R	Predictor synthesis category
-	13	0.055	-	0.871	-
polarizability	12	0.055	0	0.870	11
Δ_L^A	12	0.061	10.909	0.831	4
Δ_L	12	0.056	1.818	0.865	7
N_{atom}^D	12	0.056	1.818	0.865	6
E_g	12	0.055	0	0.868	10
λ_h	12	0.062	12.727	0.820	3
$IP(v)$	12	0.055	0	0.868	8
E_{HL}^{DA}	12	0.062	12.727	0.819	2
Δ_H	12	0.055	0	0.871	13
E_{bind}	12	0.069	25.455	0.755	1
E_{LL}^{DA}	12	0.055	0	0.870	12
Δ_{ge}	12	0.057	3.636	0.862	5
E_{TI}	12	0.055	0	0.868	9

Table 7. Sensitivity analysis for GRNN model (J_{SC} prediction).

Predictor element elimination	No. of predictors elements	SI	% of variation of SI	R	Predictor synthesis category
-	13	0.131	-	0.819	-
polarizability	12	0.132	0.763	0.807	6
Δ_L^A	12	0.1340	2.290	0.768	4
Δ_L	12	0.1454	10.992	0.749	2
N_{atom}^D	12	0.133	1.527	0.806	5
E_g	12	0.132	0.763	0.811	9
λ_h	12	0.147	12.214	0.726	1
$IP(v)$	12	0.132	0.763	0.813	10
E_{HL}^{DA}	12	0.132	0.763	0.808	8
Δ_H	12	0.143	9.160	0.758	3
E_{bind}	12	0.131	0	0.817	13
E_{LL}^{DA}	12	0.131	0	0.813	12
Δ_{ge}	12	0.131	0	0.813	11
E_{TI}	12	0.132	0.763	0.807	7

Table 8. Sensitivity analysis for GRNN model (FF prediction).

Predictor element elimination	No. of predictors elements	SI	% of variation of SI	R	Predictor synthesis category
-	13	0.088	-	0.850	-
polarizability	12	0.088	0	0.850	12
Δ_L^A	12	0.102	15.909	0.754	3
Δ_L	12	0.107	21.591	0.734	1
N_{atom}^D	12	0.089	1.136	0.842	8
E_g	12	0.103	17.046	0.752	2
λ_h	12	0.090	2.273	0.834	5
$IP(v)$	12	0.089	1.136	0.840	7
E_{HL}^{DA}	12	0.089	1.136	0.846	10
Δ_H	12	0.090	2.273	0.836	6
E_{bind}	12	0.091	3.409	0.828	4
E_{LL}^{DA}	12	0.088	0	0.849	11
Δ_{ge}	12	0.088	0	0.850	13
E_{TI}	12	0.089	1.136	0.842	9

Table 9. Sensitivity analysis for GRNN model (*PCE* prediction).

Predictor element elimination	No. of predictors elements	SI	% of variation of SI	R	Predictor synthesis category
-	13	0.163	-	0.852	-
polarizability	12	0.170	4.294	0.828	8
Δ_L^A	12	0.169	3.681	0.827	6
Δ_L	12	0.178	9.202	0.799	1
N_{atom}^D	12	0.165	1.227	0.850	12
E_g	12	0.171	4.908	0.827	7
λ_h	12	0.170	4.294	0.827	5
$IP(v)$	12	0.171	4.908	0.824	2
E_{HL}^{DA}	12	0.171	4.908	0.824	3
Δ_H	12	0.167	2.454	0.847	10
E_{bind}	12	0.172	5.521	0.825	4
E_{LL}^{DA}	12	0.165	1.227	0.850	11
Δ_{ge}	12	0.163	0.000	0.850	13
E_{TI}	12	0.169	3.681	0.832	9

First, the model for *PCE* prediction is dependent on Δ_L , as shown by the higher *SI* value (9.202%) when the Δ_L component is removed. Hence, the parameters $IP(v)$, E_{HL}^{DA} , E_{bind} , λ_h , Δ_L^A , E_g , polarizability, and E_{TI} , when excluded, raise the *SI* from 3.681% to 4.908%. Omitting the parameter Δ_H results in a reduction of the *SI* to 2.454%. Moreover, the parameters N_{atom}^D and E_{LL}^{DA} exhibit an equivalent influence of 1.227%. The parameter Δ_{ge} is not statistically significant.

4.3. Sensitivity Analysis of the GRNN Kernel Functions

Comparative analysis was conducted on the performance of the GRNN model utilizing Gaussian and reciprocal kernel functions, as depicted in Fig. 11. The findings validate the exceptional precision of both kernel functions; nevertheless, the Gaussian kernel function exhibits somewhat superior accuracy compared to the reciprocal kernel function.

Fig. 11. Comparison of the Gaussian and reciprocal kernel functions for the GRNN model.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The efficiency of organic solar cells depends on a delicate balance between various molecular, electronic, and structural properties. Achieving high V_{OC} , J_{SC} , FF , and ultimately *PCE* requires concurrently optimizing the energy levels of the donor and acceptor materials, the polarizability of the donor molecules, the reorganization energy, and the donor-acceptor interface. Effective molecular design, interface engineering, and careful management of these parameters are essential for maximizing the performance of organic solar cells.

This work used three machine learning models (GRNN, SVM, and tree boost) to estimate the performance of organic solar cells (V_{OC} , J_{SC} , FF , and PCE). The database gathered by [1] was used to train and validate the ML models. The predictive performance of each model was assessed using Taylor diagram visualization and several evaluation indices (MSE , MAE , $RMSE$, SI , and R) and compared to their gradient boosting model for PCE prediction. Based on this analysis, we can draw the following conclusions:

- i. Correlation analysis reveals that specific material characteristics, including polarizability, bandgap, dipole moment, and charge transfer, have a substantial impact on the photovoltaic performance of organic materials. Optimizing these characteristics can enhance photovoltaic performance, thereby improving short-circuit current, open-circuit voltage, fill factor, and overall power conversion efficiency. Further investigation into precise correlations and fundamental processes could provide valuable insights for designing and advancing highly effective organic photovoltaic materials. Enhancing material properties and device design to maximize the J_{SC} can substantially improve PCE . Moreover, reducing resistive losses and minimizing recombination can enhance FF , thereby greatly improving the overall PCE .
- ii. The consistently high performance of the Generalized Regression Neural Network model in predicting various solar cell performance metrics suggests that its architecture is particularly well-suited for capturing the fundamental relationships between input characteristics and target variables. The nonlinear and complex nature of solar cell performance characteristics is more accurately represented by the GRNN model compared to SVM and Tree Boost models.
- iii. The GRNN model consistently outperforms both Tree Boost and SVM models in predicting photovoltaic parameters, including V_{OC} , J_{SC} , FF , and PCE . This superior performance can be attributed to the GRNN's ability to model nonlinear relationships, handle a diverse array of input variables, and remain robust to noise and outliers. Furthermore, the GRNN's flexible kernel bandwidth facilitates more efficient training and generalization, allowing it to accommodate a broader range of input variables.
- iv. Compared to the gradient boosting model developed by Sahu *et al.*, (2018), the GRNN model significantly reduced prediction errors.
- v. Utilizing sensitivity analysis helps determine the statistical significance of the predictor variables. The key parameters for forecasting the performance metrics of organic solar cells include Δ_L , E_{bind} , Δ_L^A and Δ_{ge} . The significance of these variables is consistently high across various performance measures. Additionally, other variables such as N_{atom}^D , E_{T1} , E_{HL}^{DA} and λ_h also significantly influence the prediction of specific performance metrics.
- vi. The comparative analysis of the GRNN model's performance using Gaussian and reciprocal kernel functions indicates that while both functions performed well, the Gaussian kernel function was slightly more accurate than the reciprocal kernel function.
- vii. The results demonstrate that the GRNN model exhibits superior accuracy and precision compared to other models in predicting the performance metrics of organic solar cells, including V_{OC} , J_{SC} , FF , and PCE .

The analysis of solar cell performance prediction data identifies several features that could enhance prediction accuracy, including material properties, device structure and fabrication parameters, environmental conditions, temporal and spatial factors, and experimental uncertainties. Incorporating these features may enable machine learning models, particularly the GRNN, to better understand the complex relationships between input variables and solar cell performance, potentially leading to more accurate predictions.

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ETHICS STATEMENT

This study did not involve human or animal subjects and, therefore, did not require ethical approval.

STATEMENT OF CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflicts of interest related to this study.

LICENSING

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